

Figure S1. Spint1a-deficient SKCM shows enhanced aggressiveness in adult zebrafish allotransplantation assays. Control and Spint1a deficient SKCMs were disaggregated and 30,000 (A), 100,000 (B) and 300,000 cells (C) were injected subcutaneously in pre-irradiated adult casper zebrafish. Fish were analyzed for average tumor size (pixels) from 1 to 4 weeks post-transplant. Representative images and quantification of the average tumor size are shown. Each dot corresponds to a recipient-transplanted fish and the mean \pm SEM is also shown (n=2 SKCM tumors). *p<0.05, ***p<0.001 according to unpaired Student *t* test.

Figure S2. Expression analysis of differentiation melanocyte, EMT, inflammation and immune cell markers in zebrafish SKCM. The mRNA levels of the genes encoding the differentiation melanocyte markers *Sox10*, *Mitfa*, *Tyr* and *Dct*, the EMT markers *Cdh1*, *Slug* and *Mmp9*, the inflammation marker *Il1b*, the neutrophil markers *Lyz* and *Mpx*, the macrophage marker *Mpeg1*, and the ISGs *B2m*, *Mxb* and *Pkz* were analyzed by RT-qPCR in control and Spint1a-deficient SKCMs. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01 according to one-tailed Student *t* test.

Table S1. Primers used in this study for RT-qPCR. The gene symbols followed the Zebrafish Nomenclature Guidelines (http://zfin.org/zf_info/nomen.html/). ENA, European Nucleotide Archive (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>).

Gene	ENA ID	Name	Sequence (5'→3')
<i>rps11</i>	NM_213377	F1	GGCGTCAACGTGTCAGAGTA
		R1	GCCTCTTCTCAAAACGGTTG
<i>sox10</i>	NM_131875.1	F	CCTCACGCTACAGGTCAGAG
		R	CGAAGTCGATGTGCGGTTTC
<i>mitfa</i>	NM_001362262.1	F	CGACTGGTCAGTTCTTGAC
		R	AGGTGGGTCTGAACCTGGTA
<i>tyr</i>	NM_131013.3	F	TGTATTCATGAACGGCTCCA
		R	GATGAAGGGCACCATGAAGT
<i>dct</i>	NM_131555.2	F	TGGACAGTAAACCCTGGGGA
		R	CCGGCAAAGTTTCCAAAGCA
<i>cdh1</i>	NM_131820.1	F	TGGCAAAGACTAGGCAAAGTGAC
		R	AAACACCTTGTGGCCCTCAT
<i>slug</i>	NM_001008581.1	F1	AGTCCAACAGTGTTTATTTCTCCA
		R1	GCAGGTTGCTGGTAGTCCAT
<i>mmp9</i>	NM_213123.1	F1	GCTGCTCATGAGTTTGGACA
		R1	AGGGCCAGTTCTAGGTCCAT
<i>il1b</i>	NM_212844.2	F5	GGCTGTGTGTTTGGGAATCT
		R5	TGATAAACCAACCGGGAACA
<i>lyz</i>	NM_139180.1	F	TGGCAGTGGTGTTTTTGTGT
		R	TCAAATCCATCAAGCCCTTC
<i>mpx</i>	NM_212779	F1	AGGGCGTGACCATGCTATAC
		R1	AGGCTCAGCAACACCTCCTA
<i>mpeg1</i>	NM_212737.1	F	ACAGCAAAACACCCATCTGGCGA
		R	TGCGGCACAATCGCAGTCCA
<i>b2m</i>	NM_001159768.1	F	AACCAAACACCCTGATCTGC
		R	CAACGCTCTTTGTGAGGTGA
<i>mxh</i>	NM_001128672.1	F	AATGGTGATCCGCTATCTGC
		R	TCTGGCGGCTCAGTAAGTTT
<i>pkz</i>	NM_001040376.2	F1	GGAGCACCGTACAGGACATT
		R1	CTCGGGCTTTATTTGCTCTG